

Recombinant expression of human COX2 in insect cells using the Bac-to-Bac system and purification by ion exchange and size-exclusion chromatography

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ABSTRACT

This protocol describes the recombinant expression of human cyclooxygenase-2 (COX2) encoded by the *PTGS2* gene (RefSeq NM_000963.4) in *Spodoptera frugiperda* (*Sf9*) insect cells using the Bac-to-Bac baculovirus expression system. The method includes transformation of *E. coli* DH10Bac with pFastBac1 vector containing the full-length human *PTGS2* gene, supplied pre-assembled by GenScript, followed by selection and screening of recombinant colonies, purification and PCR verification of the bacmid DNA, transfection of *Sf9* cells, and production of P1–P3 viral stocks. Following pilot expression assays, recombinant COX2 protein is purified from infected insect cells using a detergent-based lysis protocol followed by ion exchange and size-exclusion chromatography, adapted from Gierse et al. (*Cyclooxygenases: Methods and Protocols*, 2016, Chapter 3). This strategy enables recovery of active, untagged COX2 protein suitable for biochemical and cellular studies with the COX2 protein.

METHODOLOGY

1. Transformation of *E. coli* DH10Bac with pFastBac1-PTGS2

To generate recombinant baculoviral DNA expressing human cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), the protein product of the *PTGS2* gene (RefSeq NM_000963.4), the pFastBac1-*PTGS2* plasmid supplied by GenScript—containing the full-length human *PTGS2* open reading frame under the control of the polyhedrin promoter—is used to transform *E. coli* DH10Bac cells and introduced into *E. coli* DH10Bac cells. These bacteria contain a “bacmid” (a large plasmid functioning as the baculovirus genome) and the machinery required for transposition. In the transformed bacteria, the gene of interest is transferred from the pFastBac1 vector into the bacmid. Selection is performed using a blue–white screening system, where white colonies indicate successful recombination of the gene of interest into the bacmid.

1. Prepare and plate LB-agar supplemented with kanamycin (50 µg/mL), gentamicin (7 µg/mL), tetracycline (10 µg/mL), BluO-gal (100 µg/mL), and IPTG (40 µg/mL).
2. Prepare pFastBac-COX2 plasmid (200 pg/µL in TE, pH 8.0) and competent *E. coli* DH10Bac cells on ice.
3. Pre-warm SOC medium at 37 °C.
4. Thaw the competent DH10Bac cells on ice (100 µL).
5. Add 5 µL (1 ng) of pFastBac-COX2 plasmid to the cells.
6. Incubate on ice for 30 minutes.
7. Perform heat-shock: 42 °C for 45 seconds.
8. Place immediately on ice for 2 minutes.
9. Add 900 µL of SOC medium (pre-warmed).
10. Incubate at 37 °C with shaking (225–230 rpm) for 4 hours.
11. Plate 100 µL undiluted, 1:10, and 1:100 dilutions onto selective LB-agar plates. Spread the remaining transformation mix onto an additional plate.

12. Incubate plates at 37 °C for 24–48 hours.

Figure 1. Selective agar plates showing the results of pFastBac-COX2 transformation into *E. coli* DH10Bac. White colonies indicate successful recombination of the COX2 gene into the bacmid, whereas blue colonies correspond to non-recombinant clones. The different plates represent various dilutions of the transformation mix to facilitate the isolation of individual colonies (100 μ L undiluted, 1:10, and 1:100 dilutions and the remaining).

13. Identify recombinant colonies: white (positive, gene insertion) vs blue (negative, non-recombinant), it can appear in two days (Figure 1).

Note: blue color intensifies in 3-4 days.

14. Perform colony restreaking: pick 10 white and 2 blue colonies as controls. Plate on LB-agar with antibiotics for two days to isolate the colonies. (Fig. 2)

15. Incubate overnight at 37 °C.

Figure 2. Isolation of clones on a plate by restreaking. White (positive, e.g., 9 and 10) and blue (negative, e.g., 1 and 2) colonies selected from the primary plates are streaked onto a new selective plate to obtain pure cultures before inoculation into liquid medium, ensuring that the selected colonies are completely white.

2. Bacmid DNA Purification and PCR Verification

Once the potentially recombinant white colonies have been selected, it is necessary to verify that the COX2 gene has been correctly inserted into the bacmid. In this section, bacmid DNA is isolated from several selected white colonies. Subsequently, a Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) is performed using primers flanking the insertion site to confirm the presence and correct size of the insert. This step ensures that only correctly recombined clones are used for virus production.

1. Inoculate 9 verified white colonies into 5 mL LB broth + antibiotics in 50 mL Falcon tubes and one blue colony as control.
2. Incubate overnight at 37°C with shaking (225–230 rpm).
3. Prepare glycerol stocks for long-term storage:
 - Mix 850 µL of overnight culture with 150 µL of sterile 80% glycerol (final glycerol concentration: 15%).
 - Vortex gently and freeze immediately at –80 °C.
4. Harvest the remaining culture by centrifugation: 3500 × g, 15 min, 4 °C.
5. Extract bacmid DNA using NZYMiniprep Kit® (Nzytech).
6. Quantify DNA quality and concentration using NanoDrop.
7. Perform PCR using Q5® High-Fidelity 2X Master Mix (NEB) with primers:
 - M13 Forward: 5'-CCCAGTCACGACGTTGTAAAACG-3'
 - M13 Reverse: 5'-AGCGGATAACAATTCACACAGG-3'
 - 10–15 ng bacmid DNA per reaction.

Design the PCR protocol following Polymerase instructions and use NEB T_m Calculator to determine annealing temperature (66°C).

8. Run the PCR protocol in the Thermal Cycler.
9. Prepare a 0.8% agarose gel in TAE 1x buffer:
 - Calculate agarose quantity based on gel mold volume.
 - Dissolve agarose in TAE buffer by heating in a microwave. Pause every few seconds to swirl the flask carefully, using protection to avoid burns.
 - Once fully dissolved, allow to cool to ~45–50 °C.
 - Add SERVA® DNA Stain G (or equivalent) to the molten agarose.
 - Pour gel into mold with comb in place. Allow to solidify.
10. Load PCR products alongside a DNA size marker (e.g., Thermo Fisher GeneRuler 1 kb Plus).
11. Run electrophoresis at 100 V for 90 minutes.
12. Visualize bands under a transilluminator.

13. Expected product size: ~4200 bp (2300 bp vector backbone + 1900 bp COX2 insert).
A single clear band confirms correct bacmid recombination (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Agarose gel showing PCR verification of the recombinant bacmid. Purified bacmid DNA from nine white colonies (lanes 1–9) and one blue colony (last lane) was used as template. All white clones display a band of the expected size (~4200 bp), confirming correct insertion of the COX2 gene, whereas the blue control colony is absent.

14. You can send the PCR product for DNA sequencing

3. Large-Scale Bacmid DNA Preparation

1. Select the glycerol stock colony with the cleanest PCR amplification.
2. Inoculate into 250 mL LB broth + antibiotics in a 1 L Erlenmeyer flask.
3. Grow overnight at 37 °C with shaking (225 rpm).
4. Extract and purify bacmid DNA using NZY Maxiprep Endotoxin-Free Kit®.
5. Quantify DNA and store at 4°C until use for transfection.

4. Sf9 Cell Culture and Transfection

This is the starting point for virus production. The purified bacmid DNA is introduced (transfected) into *Spodoptera frugiperda* (*Sf9*) insect cells. Inside the cells, the bacmid DNA replicates and assembles, generating the first infectious viral particles. This initial batch of virus is known as the P1 stock. The protocol details the careful handling of *Sf9* cells—from thawing to transfection optimization—to maximize the production of the initial virus.

1. Thaw from the liquid nitrogen a cryovial of *Sf9* cells ($\approx 5 \times 10^6$ cells) in a 25 °C water bath.
Note: Avoid overheating; thawing at 37 °C decreases cell viability.

2. Transfer the entire content of the vial directly into a T-25 flask containing Insect-Xpress® medium (Lonza) supplemented with antibiotic and antimycotic solution
Critical Step: Do not centrifuge the thawed cells, as this may reduce recovery.

3. Allow cells to adhere for ~3 h at 27 °C.

4. After 3 h, carefully remove the medium (which contains residual DMSO from the cryopreservation solution, toxic to cells) and replace it with fresh supplemented Insect-Xpress® medium.

Note: Removing DMSO early promotes faster recovery and reduces cell death.

5. Maintain cells in T-25 flasks at 27°C until they recover normal growth and exhibit healthy morphology. This recovery phase may take several days.

- Replace the medium every 3-4 days to remove death cells.

- Wait until the flask is fully confluent (completely covered with cells) before attempting to subculture. Early subculturing may compromise recovery and reduce cell viability.

Tip: The recovery phase can take several days. Patience is key for obtaining robust, adherent cultures

6. Subculture by detaching cells through firm tapping of the flask or by gently pipetting the medium across the surface.

Caution: Do not use trypsin, as it damages insect cells and reduces their viability. If detachment is difficult, allow a few more days until the culture reaches superconfluence, then pipette the medium firmly using a glass pipette to lift the cell sheet (Figure 4A, -B)

7. After 2–3 passages (to ensure recovery and stable growth), prepare for transfection assay.

8. Plate 2.5 mL of cells at 1×10^6 cells/mL in a 6-well plate (without antibiotics).

Note: Antibiotics can interfere with transfection efficiency and should be omitted during the assay

9. Next day, transfect using TransIT® Insect reagent according to the manufacturer (Mirus) and the following conditions:

Condition	DNA	TransIT
Control (medium only)	—	—
TransIT only	—	5 µL
DNA only	2.5 µg	—
DNA:TransIT (1:1)	2.5 µg	2.5 µL
DNA:TransIT (1:2)	2.5 µg	5 µL
DNA:TransIT (1:4)	2.5 µg	10 µL

<p>Only DNA</p>		
<p>Ratio DNA:Transit 1:4</p>		

Tip: Prepare DNA-TransIT complexes in sterile Eppendorf and incubate 15 min at room temperature before adding them dropwise to the wells.

10. Incubate at 27 °C for 72 h.

Important note: Cells become large and aberrant after transfection; this indicates baculovirus production. Compare with other wells (Figure 4)

11. Collect the culture supernatants (P1 viral stock). Store at -80°C for baculovirus amplification. 4°C for short-term.

Note: The P1 supernatants contain low-titer virus and should not be used directly for large-scale infection. Some protocols recommend filtering at 0.45

12. Lyse the remaining cells on ice adding 200 ul of lysis buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, 140 mM NaCl, 0.1% SDS, 1% Triton X-100, 1 mM EDTA, protease inhibitors).

13. Perform Western blot to confirm COX2 expression

Figure 4. Morphology of Sf9 cells under different conditions. (A) Healthy Sf9 culture with round, refractile morphology, in optimal condition. (B) Over-confluent adherent culture showing high cell density ready for subculture. (C) Sf9 cells 72 hours after baculovirus infection, showing characteristic cytopathic effects such as increased cell size, granularity, and detachment from the surface.

5. Adaptation of *Sf9* insect cells from adherent monolayer to suspension culture

Sf9 (*Spodoptera frugiperda*) cells can grow either as adherent monolayers or in suspension. Cells obtained from cryostocks are typically adherent and require stepwise adaptation to suspension growth to maintain viability and achieve high-density cultures for large-scale baculovirus production and recombinant protein expression. Proper adaptation minimizes stress and ensures consistent morphology, growth rate, and infection efficiency.

1. Grow *Sf9* cells in T-25 flasks with Insect-Xpress® medium at 27°C until 100% confluent.
Note: Ensure cells are completely confluent in the flask, healthy, refractile, and free from contamination (Figure 4B)
2. Remove spent medium and gently resuspend cells in fresh medium
3. Detach the cells by tapping the flask or pipetting the medium across the surface
Important: Do not use trypsin because enzymatic treatment reduces viability.
4. Count cells and check its viability
5. Transfer the detached cells to a 125 mL vented shaker flask containing 25 mL fresh Insect-Xpress® medium at final density: $\sim 1 \times 10^6$ cells/mL.
6. Place the flask in a 27 °C shaker incubator at 100 rpm.
Tip: Start with lower agitation (80 rpm) to minimize shear stress.
7. Allow cells to settle and adapt for 2–3 days. Monitor morphology daily.
8. Subculture when the cell density reaches $4\text{--}6 \times 10^6$ cells/mL
9. At each passage, seed 1×10^6 cells/mL in 50 mL medium in a 125 mL flask.
10. Continue adaptation until viability >95% for at least three consecutive passages, and doubling time stabilizes ($\sim 24\text{--}30$ h).

6. Baculovirus Amplification (P1 → P2 → P3)

The initial viral stock (P1) obtained from the transfection has a titer (concentration of infectious virus) that is too low for large-scale protein production. Therefore, amplification is required. This process involves using the P1 stock to infect a small *Sf9* cell culture, generating a higher-titer P2 stock. The process is then repeated, using the P2 to infect a larger culture and produce a final high-titer P3 stock, suitable for expression experiments.

1. Identify the optimal P1 baculovirus stock (from Step 4) based on Western blot analysis. Use the P1 stock corresponding to the condition showing the best COX2 expression for subsequent infections.
Note: The viral titer of P1 is typically low ($10^6\text{--}10^7$ pfu/mL); use it only for infection of small-scale cultures to amplify viral stocks.

2. Prepare fresh *Sf9* cell cultures for infection: Subculture cells from maintenance flasks into vented 125 mL Erlenmeyer flasks at a density of 1.25×10^6 cells/mL (20 mL total volume).
3. Incubate overnight at 27 °C, 100 rpm, so that the next day the cultures reach 2×10^6 cells/mL, optimal for infection.
4. Calculate the inoculum volume required for infection using the following formula:

$$\text{Inoculum (mL)} = \frac{\text{MOI (pfu/cell)} \times \text{Number of cells}}{\text{Viral titer (pfu/mL)}}$$

where MOI (multiplicity of infection) should be 0.05–0.1.

Note: If the viral titer is unknown, assume 10^6 – 10^7 pfu/mL for the P1 stock as an initial estimate.

Critical Step: An excessively high MOI may cause premature cell death and lower virus yield

5. Infect *Sf9* cells at MOI = 0.1, when the culture reaches 2×10^6 cells/mL.
6. Incubate at 27 °C, shaking 100 rpm, for 72 h.
7. Harvest culture supernatant (P2 stock) by centrifugation: 500 × g, 10 min, 4 °C.
Tip: If a refrigerated centrifuge is not available, centrifugation at room temperature is acceptable for short spins.
8. Store clarified supernatant (P2) at 4°C.
Note: Expected P2 stock titer between 1×10^7 and 1×10^8 pfu/mL.
9. Scale up to produce the P3 viral stock.
 - Inoculate 200 mL of *Sf9* cells at 2×10^6 cells/mL in a 1 L vented flask.
 - Use an MOI of 0.1, assuming a P2 titer between 1×10^7 and 1×10^8 pfu/mL.
 - Incubate at 27 °C, shaking at 100 rpm for 72 h.
10. Collect the P3 supernatant as before (centrifuge 500 × g, 10 min, 4 °C).
Note: The P3 stock typically reaches a titer of 1×10^8 – 10^9 pfu/mL and is suitable for large-scale protein expression assays.
11. Store P3 aliquots at 4°C and -80°C for long-term use. Avoid multiple freeze–thaw cycles to preserve infectivity.

Comments:

- Monitor infection daily: healthy cells appear small and round; infected cells enlarge, check cell viability every day it should be reduce.
- Use vented flasks allowing proper aeration. Oxygen limitation reduces viral yield.
- Keep one uninfected *Sf9* flask as a control to assess morphological changes caused by infection.
- Avoid antibiotics during amplification, as they may affect viral propagation.

7. Pilot protein expression assay

This section describes a small-scale infection assay to evaluate the expression kinetics of recombinant COX2 using the high-titer P3 baculovirus stock and checking different time and MOI infection.

1. Prepare two 250 mL vented flasks, each containing 70 mL of *Sf9* cells at a density of 2×10^6 cells/mL in Insect-Xpress® medium (without antibiotics).
2. Calculate the inoculum volume required for infection according to the desired multiplicity of infection (MOI):

- For MOI = 5:

$$\begin{aligned} & (5 \text{ pfu/cell} \times 2 \times 10^6 \text{ cells/mL} \times 60 \text{ mL}) / 0.5 \times 10^9 \text{ pfu/mL} \\ & = 1.2 \text{ mL of P3 stock} \end{aligned}$$

- For MOI = 10:

$$\begin{aligned} & (10 \text{ pfu/cell} \times 2 \times 10^6 \text{ cells/mL} \times 60 \text{ mL}) / 0.5 \times 10^9 \text{ pfu/mL} \\ & = 2.4 \text{ mL of P3 stock} \end{aligned}$$

Note: example calculation assumes a P3 titer of 0.5×10^9 pfu/mL.

3. Collect a negative control by collecting 10 mL of uninfected cells (before infection), centrifuging at $5000 \times g$ for 20 min at 4 °C, discarding the supernatant, and freezing the pellet at -80 °C.

Note: This uninfected control will serve as a baseline for Western blot analysis of COX2 expression.

4. Infect one flask with the 5 MOI and the other with the 10 MOI using the volumes calculated above.
 - Mix gently to distribute virus evenly.
 - Incubate both flasks at 27°C, shaking at 100 rpm.
5. Collect time-course samples to monitor infection and expression dynamics:
 - Withdraw 10 mL aliquots from each flask at 24 h, 48 h, 72 h, and 96 h post-infection.
 - Pellet cells by centrifugation at $5000 \times g$, 20 min, 4°C, discard the supernatant, and freeze pellets at -80 °C for later protein extraction.
6. Observe and check cell viability of the cultures daily under the microscope to monitor infection progression:
 - Infected cells will appear larger, more granular, and less adherent.
 - An increase in death cells indicates late-stage infection or cell lysis.
7. Analyze COX2 expression by Western blotting using lysates from each time point to determine the optimal harvest time (Figure 5)

Note: Peak expression in *Sf9* cells typically occurs between 48 h and 72 h post-infection, but timing can vary depending on the protein and viral load.

Figure 5. Analysis of COX2 expression by Western blot to optimize harvest time. *Sf9* cells were infected at a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 5 and 10. Samples were collected at 24, 48, and 72 hours post-infection. The blot, probed with an anti-COX-2 antibody, shows that protein expression (~70 kDa band) reaches its maximum at 48 and for both MOIs, better at 5 MOI.

8. Protein extraction and purification

This protocol describes COX2 protein purification from cell pellets derived from one flask containing 100 mL infected *Sf9* culture with 0,5 MOI (harvested at ~48 h, 2×10^6 cells/mL).

A. Cell resuspension and pellet wash (cold; keep everything on ice)

1. Resuspend pellet: For a ~100 mL cell culture, resuspend the pellet in 20 mL Homogenization Buffer (HB) (no detergent). Add protease inhibitor (fresh PMSF and protease inhibitor cocktail) at resuspension.
2. Rock the suspension at room temperature for 30 min to equilibrate (gentle rocking).
3. Centrifuge homogenate at $10,000 \times g$ for 20 min (4 °C). Discard the supernatant
Note: at this point the target protein remains in the pellet.
4. Prepare 15% C10M detergent stock: weigh 0.3 g C10M and dissolve in 2 mL HB → this is 15% (w/v) stock.

B. Detergent solubilization (membrane extraction)

5. Resuspend pellet in 18 mL HB (cold) and add the 2 mL of 15% C10M stock dropwise while gently mixing to reach 1.5% final C10M. Add protease inhibitors if not already present.

Critical Step: add detergent slowly (dropwise) to avoid local over-concentration and precipitation. Maintain sample at 4°C.

6. Extract by gentle rotation for 1 hour at 4 °C to solubilize membrane COX-2.
7. Clarify the extract by centrifugation at 25,000 × g for 20 min at 4 °C. Collect the supernatant (detergent extract) — this is the material to load on the anion (ion) exchange column (AIEX).

Note: Save a 20–50 µL aliquot for SDS-PAGE.

C. Pre-column filtration and AIEX equilibration

8. Filter the clarified extract through a 0.45 µm filter (syringe) into a sample container ready for SuperLoop loading (20 mL load).
9. Equilibrate AIEX column: equilibrate with 2 CV Buffer A.

D. Anion exchange chromatography (AIEX)

10. Load: inject 20 mL of filtered extract into the SuperLoop and load onto the QFF column.
11. Wash with 3 CV Buffer A (≈ 60 mL) to remove unbound material.
12. Elute with a linear salt gradient 0 → 100% Buffer B (0 → 300 mM NaCl) over 2 CV (≈ 40 mL) at 2 mL/min (adapt flow to column). Monitor UV 280. The protein typically elutes on the leading edge of the main peak (Figure 6).

Fraction collection: collect ~2 mL fractions starting from ~50% of the gradient. In practice, target fractions 18–24 (these numbers correspond to the example/run described in the optimized protocol; the protein began to elute at ~36 mL after starting

Figure 6. Results of purification by anion-exchange chromatography. Top: Chromatogram showing the elution profile with a salt gradient. The red box indicates the main peak where the COX-2 protein elutes. Blue lane UV at 280 nm, brown lane conductivity, green lane gradient elution. Bottom: Coomassie-stained SDS-PAGE gel showing the protein content of the collected fractions (B1–C7). Fractions with the highest COX2 purity (around B7–C2) were selected for subsequent purification steps.

gradient).

13. Post-elution wash: wash column with 2 CV of 1 M NaCl to strip remaining bound proteins.
14. Choose and pool the fractions with highest purity/protein (in the example this corresponded to ~14 mL total volume). (Gel Figure 6)

E. Concentration for SEC

15. Concentrate pooled AIEX fractions using Amicon 30 kDa centrifugal concentrator to approximately 0.5 mL (or volume compatible with SEC injection). Pre-wet and use the concentrator membrane per manufacturer instructions.

F. Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) (Superdex 200 10/300 GL)

16. Equilibrate SEC: wash column with 2 CV SEC buffer (≈ 50 mL) before sample injection.
17. Inject 0.5 mL concentrated sample onto Superdex 200 10/300 GL. Run at 0.25 mL/min and collect 0.5 mL fractions. Protein typically elutes at ~ 0.5 CV (~ 10 mL) — in practice the detergent vesicle peak (protein in detergent micelles/vesicles) appears around fractions ~ 9 – 14 (Figure 7).
18. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE and/or activity assay; pool the fractions corresponding to the main COX-2 peak.

Figure 7. Results of the final purification by size-exclusion chromatography (Superdex 200). Top: Chromatogram showing a main peak corresponding to the purified COX-2 protein. Bottom: SDS-PAGE gel of the collected fractions (A6–C9) under the main peak. A single sharp band at the expected position (~ 70 kDa) confirms the high purity of the final COX-2 protein. The “Conc” lane corresponds to the concentrated sample prior to loading onto the column.

G. Final concentration and storage

19. Concentrate pooled SEC fractions to desired concentration using Amicon (30 kDa), and measure protein concentration.
20. Run SDS-PAGE, Coomassie blue stain for quality control
21. Aliquot, quick-freeze (dry ice / ethanol) and store at -80°C . Avoid repeated freeze-thaw; for activity assays reconstitute with heme immediately before use.

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https://documents.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/LSG/manuals/MAN0000414_BactoBacExpressionSystem_UG.pdf

REAGENTS AND EQUIPMENT - TABLES

REAGENTS			
Name	Catalog Number	Supplier	Comments
pFastBac1-PTGS2 plasmid	—	GenScript	200 pg/μL in TE, pH 8.0
<i>E. coli</i> DH10Bac cells	10361012	Gibco	Chemically competent cells for Bacmid recombination
Tryptone	MB16701	NZYtech	For LB Broth and agar plates
Yeast Extract	Y1625	Sigma-Aldrich	For LB Broth and agar plates
Agar granulated	MB02903	NZYtech	For LB agar plates
Kanamycin	K1377	Sigma-Aldrich	In dH ₂ O for selective plates (10 mg/mL)
Gentamicin	G1914	Sigma-Aldrich	In dH ₂ O for selective plates (7 mg/mL)
Tetracycline	T3258	Sigma-Aldrich	In 100% ethanol for selective plates (10 mg/mL)
Bluo-gal	B2904	Sigma-Aldrich	In DMSO for elective plates (20 mg/mL)
IPTG	I6758	Sigma-Aldrich	In dH ₂ O, aliquoted (200 mg/mL)
SOC medium	15544034	Invitrogen	Pre-warmed to 37°C
Glycerol	G5516	Sigma-Aldrich	For recombinant bacterial glycerol stock
NZYMiniprep Kit	MB01002	Nzytech	For bacmid mini-prep
Q5 High-Fidelity 2X Master Mix	M0492S	NEB	For PCR screening
M13 Forward primer	—	IDT	CCCAGTCACGACGTTGTAAAACG
M13 Reverse primer	—	IDT	AGCGGATAACAATTTTCACACAGG
Agarose	16500100	Invitrogen	For electrophoresis
TAE buffer (50x)	B49	Thermo Scientific	Dilute to 1x
SERVA DNA Stain G	39803	SERVA	For DNA electrophoresis and visualization
DNA ladder 1 kb Plus	SM1331	Thermo	Size reference in DNA electrophoresis
NZY Maxiprep Endotoxin-Free Kit	MB16201	Nzytech	For bacmid purification
<i>Sf9</i> insect cells	-	In-house	From UMU cell bank

Insect-Xpress Medium	12-730Q	Lonza	Serum-free insect medium
Antibiotic Antimycotic Solution (100x)	A5955	Sigma-Aldrich	Prevention in cell culture
TransIT Insect Transfection Reagent	MIR6100	Mirus	For <i>Sf9</i> transfection
6-well culture plates	3516	Corning	Sterile for <i>Sf9</i> transfection
T-25 cell culture flasks	430639	Corning	Vented caps
Shaker Flasks	11775263	Fisherbrand	For cell culture and infection
Tris-HCl	T3253	Sigma-Aldrich	Component of buffers (1 M)
NaCl	S7653	Sigma-Aldrich	Component of buffers (4 M)
SDS	L3771	Sigma-Aldrich	Component of buffers (10%)
Sucrose	S0389	Sigma-Aldrich	Component of buffers
EDTA	E6758	Sigma-Aldrich	Component of buffers (0.2 M)
Protease inhibitor cocktail	P8849	Sigma-Aldrich	Add fresh to lysis buffer
PMSF	P7626	Sigma-Aldrich	0.5 mM final
Decyl- β -D-maltoside (C10M)	25704	Cayman Chemical	Detergent 1.5% final
n-Octyl-beta-D-glucopyranoside (BOG)	15478719	Thermo Scientific	Detergent
Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (DEDTC)	228680	Sigma-Aldrich	0.1 mM final
Pre-cast polyamide gel	NP0341BOX	Invitrogen	For SDS-PAGE
MES SDS Running Buffer (20x)	NP0002	Invitrogen	For SDS-PAGE
Sample Buffer 4x	NP0008	Invitrogen	For SDS-PAGE
BSA	MB47002	NZYtech	For Western-blotting (2% final)

QC Colloidal Coomassie Stain	1610803	Bio-Rad	For SDS-PAGE gel staining
Eppendorf tubes	0030123611	Eppendorf	—
Anti-COX2 antibody	???	???	???
Goat anti-Rabbit IgG Secondary antibody, DyLight 800	SA510036	Invitrogen	For Western-blotting (1:5000 dilution)
Anion exchange column	28936543	Cytiva	Q Sepharose Fast Flow (QFF) 16/10
Size-exclusion column	28990944	Cytiva	Superdex 200 10/300 GL
0.45 μ m filter	HPWP04700	Millipore	For buffer filtration
30 kDa cutoff centrifugal concentrator	UFC9030	Millipore	For protein concentration

EQUIPMENT

Equipment	Model / Catalog No.	Supplier	Comments
Biosafety cabinet (Class II)	Bio II Advance Plus	Telstar	For cell culture handling
Bunsen burner	—	—	For bacterial handling
Bacterial Incubator	—	Memmert	37 °C for bacterial culture plates
Bacterial shaking incubator	Multitron	Infors HT	37 °C, 225–230 rpm for bacterial liquid cultures
Cell culture Incubator	MCO-170M	Pannasonic	27 °C, static for insect cell growing
Cell culture orbital shaker incubator	Multitron	Infors HT	27 °C, 100 rpm for insect cell suspensions
Microcentrifuge (1.5–2 mL tubes, refrigerated)	5424R	Eppendorf	For processing DNA/protein samples
Spectrophotometer (NanoDrop™)	ND-2000	Thermo Scientific	For DNA quantification
Thermal cycler	T100	Bio-Rad	For PCR screening
Agarose gel electrophoresis system	Sub-Cell GT	Bio-Rad	For DNA electrophoresis
Gel documentation system	ChemiDoc MP	Bio-Rad	For gel documentation and visualization
Sonicator	Vibra-Cell VCX130	Sonics	For cell lysis
Electrophoresis Gel Tank	A25977	Invitrogen	For SDS-PAGE
Gel Transfer Device	15502897	Invitrogen	iBlot 2 for Western blotting transfer
Refrigerated ultracentrifuge	Optima™	Beckman Coulter	For large-scale virus/protein prep
FPLC system	UPC900	GE AKTA	For chromatography purification
4°C fridge and -20 °C freezer	—	—	For reagents
-80 °C freezer	—	—	For protein storage
Pipettes (0.1–10 µL, 10–100 µL, 100–1000 µL)	Research Plus	Eppendorf	With sterile tips
Inverted microscoped	CKX31	Olympus	To monitor cell morphology
Cell counter	TC20	Bio-Rad	To check cell viability
Rocking platform /tube rotator	BS-010133-AAG	BioSan	For rocking samples

IN-HOUSE BUFFERS AND SOLUTIONS

Buffer / Solution	Composition (final conc.)	Preparation	Storage
LB agar	10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, 10 g/L NaCl, 15 g/L agar	Dissolve, autoclave 20 min at 121 °C, pour 25 mL into 10 mm Petri dish	4°C
LB broth	10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, 10 g/L NaCl	Autoclave 20 min at 121 °C, cool, add antibiotics	RT
Homogenization buffer (HB)	25 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.1, 250 mM sucrose, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM DEDTC	Add DEDTC fresh, filter 0.45 µm	4 °C
Buffer A (AIEX)	20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.1, 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.1 mM DEDTC, 0.15 % C10M	Add DEDTC and detergent fresh. Filter 0.45 µm	4 °C
Buffer B (AIEX elution)	20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.1, 300 mM NaCl, 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.1 mM DEDTC, 0.15 % C10M	Add DEDTC and detergent fresh. Filter 0.45 µm	4 °C
SEC buffer	25 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.1, 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.1 mM DEDTC, 0.3 % β-OG	Filter 0.45 µm	4 °C